

PHARMACOGNOSTIC STUDY OF DENTAL COLLECTION OF MEDICINAL PLANTS

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Relevance: monophytopreparations, consisting of a single medicinal plant, demonstrate lower efficacy compared to herbal mixtures that combine several components. This treatment approach, with its broader spectrum of action, allows physicians to offer patients a more comprehensive therapeutic effect.

Research Objective: To determine the authenticity of medicinal plants included in a dental herbal mixture.

Materials and Methods: To assess authenticity, the methods of the State Pharmacopoeia of the Republic of Kazakhstan (1st edition) were used. The study objects included crushed aerial parts of sage, peppermint leaves, chamomile flowers, and oak bark.

Results and Conclusions: A pharmacognostic analysis was conducted on peppermint leaves, chamomile flowers, oak bark, and the aerial part of sage to ensure data reliability.

Macroscopic analysis was carried out on raw materials of peppermint, chamomile, common oak, and medicinal sage in accordance with the requirements of the State Pharmacopoeia of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 1st edition.

Folia piperitae: The upper surface of the leaf displays epidermal cells with slightly sinuous walls, capitate hairs, and essential oil glands. The lower surface shows epidermal cells with sinuous walls, capitate and multicellular hairs, and essential oil glands. Along the vein, elongated epidermal cells with straight walls are found.

Chamomile flowers: On the inner side of the petal, epidermal cells with sinuous walls, anomocytic stomata, and papillose hairs are observed. On the outer side, the epidermal cells are narrow with pronounced walls, anomocytic stomata, and multicellular hairs. Essential oil glands and epidermal cells with a crystal-bearing sheath were also detected.

Cortex Quercus robur: In longitudinal section, pigment-containing reservoirs aligned with the cells, groups of bast fibers with a crystal-bearing sheath, and cortical parenchyma with pigment reservoirs were identified. The transverse section shows the arrangement of bast fibers, reservoirs with transparent contents, and stone cells.

Herba Salvia: Microscopy was performed on stems, leaves, and nutlets. The upper side of the leaf contains epidermal cells with slightly sinuous walls, unicellular hairs, essential oil glands, and anomocytic stomata. On the lower side, epidermal cells with sinuous walls, anomocytic stomata, and cuticle are present. Along the vascular bundles, elongated epidermal cells can be seen. The aerial parts also exhibit unicellular hairs, capitate glands, and essential oil glands.

Stem microscopy revealed the arrangement of xylem, phloem, storage parenchyma, and primary dermal tissue. Open vascular bundles were found in the stems.

Nutlet microscopy showed that the dermal tissue contains polygonal epidermal cells, while the inner part contains oval or round-shaped storage parenchyma.

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Conclusion: The results obtained during the study confirmed the authenticity of the medicinal plants.